

CESSDA Pilot Node

CESSDA Social Science Thematic Pilot.
Interoperability services integrated with the EOSC Beyond Network of Pilot Nodes

FACTSHEET FOR: Researchers; Policy makers and authorities, national;
Education/training organisation/learners; Research Infrastructures

Pilot Node Profile

The CESSDA Pilot Node, a virtual implementation within the EOSC Beyond piloting activities, leverages a hybrid integration of existing CESSDA services and new EOSC Beyond federating capabilities to enhance the discoverability, accessibility, and interoperability of Social Science data across Europe.

Pilot Core Services

- **AAI**
Federated login to access services {production}
- **Discovery Hub**
Discover relevant studies & instruments {production}
- **Helpdesk**
Request support {production}
- **Service Catalogue**
Onboard Exchange services {beta}
- **Service Monitoring**
Availability and reliability of Exchange services {production}

EOSC Beyond Core Innovation Sandbox

A pre-production environment where a large range of users, from researchers to node operators, can test the latest developments of the EOSC core.
It acts as a Federator Node offering Core Federating Capabilities for the Pilot Nodes.

Pilot Exchange Services

- **CESSDA Data Catalogue**
(data discovery)
- **CESSDA Vocabulary Service**
(manage research data)
- **CESSDA European Language Social Science Thesaurus**
(manage research data)
- **CESSDA Data Archiving Guide**
(manage research data)
- **CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide**
(manage research data)

User story at-a-glance

1. **As a Researcher (social scientist)**
I want to use the same instrument for my research that was used in other similar research projects to be able to more easily compare data later.
2. **As a Researcher (social scientist)**
I need access to data on women's political behaviour in Greece.
 - **Persona:** Social scientist researching comparative survey data.
 - **Goal:** Use the same instruments as previous studies to ensure comparability.
 - **Before:** Manual discovery, disconnected catalogues, long wait times.
 - **After:** 2-click access to prior studies and tools via EOSC Discovery Hub.

CESSDA Node integrations with the Core Innovation Sandbox and other Pilot Nodes

Integrated Core Federating Capabilities from the Core Innovation Sandbox

- Service Catalogue
- AAI/AAI
- Discovery Hub

Integrated services from other Pilot Nodes

- Instruct ERIC Aria

Value of the Node piloting activities

The integration of CESSDA service with Core Federating Capabilities delivered by EOSC Beyond introduces advanced functionalities that enhance data discoverability, accessibility, and interoperability across different research contexts and institutional boundaries. The virtual nature of the CESSDA Pilot Node enables it to leverage distributed resources efficiently while presenting users with a unified interface for accessing Social Science data and related services, as well as resources made available by other Nodes. This architecture supports use cases where researchers need to combine resources (data, compute, storage etc.) from multiple

sources and collaborate with colleagues across different institutions and countries.

Future thematic nodes could use the experience derived from the social science domain and be informed on the processes and technical requirements to become an EOSC Node.

Finally, thematic Nodes could also be instrumental in the discussion around the sustainability of EOSC Core and foster Open Science and EOSC usage, to social science researchers.

Next steps

Initial testing has demonstrated the viability of the virtual node architecture and validated several key technical approaches for federated data access and service discovery. Collaboration with the other EOSC Beyond Pilot Nodes has facilitated knowledge sharing and accelerated the development of innovative solutions that

benefit the entire research community.

The next steps are to test and verify the various components of the CESSDA Pilot Node, in terms of their individual features, their combined capabilities and the degree to which the whole is federated with the other Pilot Nodes.

About EOSC Beyond

www.eosc-beyond.eu

The ambition of EOSC Beyond is to support the growth of the EOSC in terms of integrated providers and active users by providing new Core technical solutions that allow developers of scientific application environments to easily compose a diverse portfolio of EOSC Resources, offering them as integrated capabilities to researchers.

Useful Links

CESSDA Pilot Node:

<https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/pilot/cessda>

CESSDA Pilot Node: EOSC Beyond Webinar:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15703486>

The CESSDA Pilot Node:

www.egi.eu/magazine/issue-03/eosc-beyond-the-cessda-pilot-node/

